

An Attempt to Account Quantitatively the Electro-viscous Effect of Sols of Sodium-Carboxy-methyl Cellulose under Different Conditions

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It has been shown that Smoluchowski equation for electroviscous effect as modified by the author can be used to account quantitatively for the variation of the reduced viscosity, η_{sp}/C , of sodium-carboxy-methyl cellulose (SCMC) sol under such conditions as (1) dilution of the sol with water, (2) alteration of its pH by the addition of an acid or alkali and (3) its dilution with solutions of salts like NaCl, KCl etc., the concentration of the salts being fixed at the desired levels.

It has also been shown that the specific conductivity of the sol is made up of two parts, one part contributed by the macromolecules with their electrical double layers and the other part by the small ions present in the dispersion medium and that the specific conductivity associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layers of the macromolecules does not change appreciably with dilution although the macromolecules undergo slight hydrolysis.

In previous publications¹⁻³ it has been shown how Smoluchowski equation for electro-viscous effect of colloids has been modified by the author and the modified equation has been used to account for the viscous properties of a number of colloidal electrolytes and ampholytes quantitatively.

In this paper the application of the modified equation to account for the reduced viscosity, η_{sp}/C of (SCMC) sols under different conditions will be discussed.

Basu and Das Gupta⁴ have investigated at 35° the viscous properties of (SCMC) sol under such conditions as (1) its dilution with water, (2) alteration of its pH by the addition of an acid or alkali and (3) its dilution with solutions of salts like NaCl, KCl, etc., the concentrations of the salts being fixed at the desired levels. They⁴ have observed that the pH of a 0.04% sol in distilled water is 6.8. Since the pH of (Laboratory) distilled water lies between 6.2 and 6.4, their observation indicates that (SCMC) undergoes slight hydrolysis in water.

The variation of η_{sp}/C with the dilution of (SCMC) by water has been accounted for by using an empirical equation proposed by Fuoss but its variation under other conditions has been explained only qualitatively by the authors⁴.

Deduction of the equations :

(1) The Einstein-Smoluchowski equation for electro-viscous effect has been modified by substituting the specific conductivity λ of the sol in place of λ_s the specific conductivity of the dispersion medium and may

be written as follows

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K \frac{V}{100} \left[1 + \frac{1}{\eta_0 a^2 \lambda} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots(1)$$

It has been shown in previous publications⁵⁻⁷ that the variation of λ with the concentration C (unit arbitrary) of the colloid in the sol can be represented by the following equation :

$$\lambda = \theta \lambda_s + (1 - \theta) \lambda_d \quad \dots(2)$$

In equation (1) V is the specific volume of the colloidal material, C the concentration in gram per 100 ml. of the sol, K , a constant equal to 2.5 for spherical particles η_0 and D the viscosity and dielectric constant of the dispersion medium, a the radius and ζ the electro kinetic potential of the particles.

In equation (2) λ_s represents the specific conductivity associated with a unit area of the diffuse double layers (of the particles) at the plane of contact with the surface of an electrode of the conductivity cell and θ the fraction per unit area of the electrode surface in contact with the double layers (of the particles) and it is equal to $C/(K_0 + C)$, where K_0 is a constant.

Substituting the value of λ in equation (1) and putting $A = \frac{1}{\eta_0 a^2} \left(\frac{D}{2\pi} \right)^2$ it can be written, after simp-

lification, as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K \frac{V}{100} \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2(C + K_0)}{\lambda_s(C + K_0\lambda_i/\lambda_s)} \right] \quad \dots(3)$$

$$= k_1 \frac{m + C}{m_0 + C} \quad \dots(4)$$

In equation (4), $k_1 = K \frac{V}{100} \left(\frac{A\zeta^2 + \lambda_s}{\lambda_s} \right)$,

$m = K_0 \frac{(A\zeta^2 + \lambda_i)}{(A\zeta^2 + \lambda_s)}$ and $m_0 = K_0\lambda_i/\lambda_s$ and they remain

constant when C is varied. When the (SCMC) sol is diluted with water, η_{sp}/C should vary according to equation (4).

(2) When to a sol of (SCMC) at constant concentration an electrolyte such as an acid or alkali is added, ζ in equation (3) diminishes and λ_i increases. λ_s also changes slightly but its change can be neglected compared to that of λ_i . Let us assume that ζ changes to $\zeta[1 - a(s - s_0)]$ and λ_i changes to $\lambda_i[1 + b(s - s_0)]$ where s_0 represents the initial activity of the H^+ or OH^- ions when no acid or alkali has been added and s the activity of the ion concerned after some acid or alkali has been added. The aforesaid assumption of linear variation of ζ and λ_i with s should hold good so long as the variation of s is not large. Substituting the aforesaid values of ζ and λ_i in equation (3) and taking the ratio of $(\eta_{sp}/C)_s$ and $(\eta_{sp}/C)_0$ and simplifying in the same way as has been done in a previous publication⁸ the following relation is obtained

$$R = (\eta_{sp}/C)_s : (\eta_{sp}/C)_0 = 1 - \frac{m(s - s_0)}{m_0 + (s - s_0)} \quad \dots(5)$$

where $(\eta_{sp}/C)_s$ and $(\eta_{sp}/C)_0$ denote the observed values of the reduced viscosities when the activities of the H^+ or OH^- ions are s and s_0 respectively and m and m_0 are constants.

Equation (5) may be used to account for the variation of the ratio R with the increase of H^+ or OH^- ion activities when an acid or alkali is added to the (SCMC) sol.

(3) When a (SCMC) sol is diluted with a salt solution of sufficiently low but constant concentration its degree of hydrolysis increases as the pH of a salt solution⁹ in distilled water is considerably lower than 6.8, the pH of the (SCMC) sol. Therefore, when the concentration of (SCMC), starting from a very low value, is increased gradually in the presence of a fixed but sufficiently low concentration of a salt like NaCl its degree of hydrolysis decreases and consequently the electric charge of its macromolecules increases since the $COONa$ groups are far more strongly dissociated than the $COOH$

groups. † Under this condition the potential of the macromolecules increases with the concentration of (SCMC) and reaches a limiting value, say ζ_m , determined by the concentration of the added salt. Let us assume that ζ increases with the (SCMC) concentration C , according to the equation $\zeta = \zeta_0(1 + bc)$, where ζ_0 is the value of ζ when c is nearly zero and b is the coefficient of increment. As c increases ζ increases at first but when the limiting value ζ_m is reached it does not increase any further with c . Substituting $\zeta_0(1 + bc)$ for ζ in equation (3) and neglecting terms involving c^2 it may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K \frac{V}{100} \left[1 + A\zeta_0^2(1 + 2bc) \left\{ \frac{C + K_0}{\lambda_s(C + K_0\lambda_i/\lambda_s)} \right\} \right] \quad \dots(6)$$

When C is very small compared to K_0 and $K_0\lambda_i/\lambda_s$ in the expression $(C + K_0)/(C + K_0\lambda_i/\lambda_s)$ in equation (6) then it may be neglected and equation (6) after simplification may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = B + DC \quad \dots(6a)$$

Where $B = \left(K \frac{V}{100} \right) (1 + A\zeta_0^2/\lambda_i)$ and $D = \left(K \frac{V}{100} \right) (2bA$

$\zeta_0^2/\lambda_i)$ and they remain constant when C is varied, the range of variation being small.

Again after ζ reaches the limiting value ζ_m further increase of C does not change ζ_m and equation (6) under this condition assumes the same form as equation (4).

Therefore, in the presence of a sufficiently low but fixed concentration of an added salt as C is increased, starting from a very low concentration, η_{sp}/C should increase linearly with C according to equation (6a) until C approaches that value at which ζ becomes nearly equal to ζ_m . After this value of C is reached if it is further increased then η_{sp}/C should diminish according to equation (4).

It is to be noted, however, that as the concentration of the added salt, say NaCl, is increased the ratio of the activities of $Na^+ : H^+$ in the dispersion medium increases and this tends to suppress the degree of hydrolysis of (SCMC) owing to common ion effect and also according to Donnan's theory of membrane equilibrium. Furthermore, it may be noted that the higher the concentration of the added salt in the (SCMC) sol, the lower must be the ζ of the macromolecules in the sol. Therefore, at a sufficiently high salt concentration, rise of ζ as C is increased, starting from a low concentration, should not occur and at the same time the value of ζ should be quite small. Under this condition, λ_i and $K_0\lambda_i$ should have high values and when C is very small compared to $K_0\lambda_i/\lambda_s$ in the denominator in the right hand side of equation (3) then it may be

† Strictly speaking ζ varies inversely as h , the degree of hydrolyses and if h varies inversely as \sqrt{c} , then ζ should vary as \sqrt{c} , so one may also write $\zeta = \zeta_0(1 + b\sqrt{c})$

neglected and equation (3) may be written as follows :

$$\eta_{sp}/C = K \frac{V}{100} \left[1 + \frac{A\zeta^2(K_0 + C)}{K_0\lambda_i} \right] = B_1 + D_1 C \quad \dots(6b)$$

where $B_1 = (kV/100) (1 + A\zeta^2/\lambda_i)$ and $D_1 = (KV/100) (A\zeta^2 K_0 \lambda_i)$ and they remain constant when C is varied.

It, therefore, follows from equation (6b) that when the concentration of the added salt is fixed at a sufficiently high level, η_{sp}/C should vary linearly with C , the concentration of (SCMC).

(4) In previous publications⁵⁻⁷ it has been shown that equation (2) holds good for colloids which do not undergo hydrolysis in water. Since (SCMC) undergoes slight hydrolysis in aqueous solution so in this case the validity of equation (2) should be checked.

In equation (2) $\theta = C/(K_0 + C)$ and where C is very small compared to K_0 it may be neglected. Therefore it follows that,

$$\lambda = \left(\frac{C}{K_0 + C} \right) \lambda_s + \lambda_i \left(1 - \frac{C}{K_0 + C} \right) = C\lambda'_s + \lambda_i \quad \dots(7)$$

Neglecting $C/(K_0 + C)$ compared to unity when C is very small compared to K_0 and $\lambda'_s = (\lambda_s/K_0)$. The data recorded in Table 5 confirm the validity of equation (7) and hence that of equation (2).

Notes on the data recorded in the Tables :

TABLE 1—(VARIATION OF η_{sp}/C WITH C IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AT 35°C)

Miscellaneous	(SCMC) per cent C	Variation of η_{sp}/C	
		Observed	Calculated
Eqn. - (4)	0.070	63.5	60.5
$K_1 = 51$	0.053	63.1	63.2
$m = 0.017$	0.040	68.0	67.5
$m_0 = 0.0033$	0.023	76.6	77.6
	0.013	93.2	93.8

TABLE 2(a)—(VARIATION OF R WITH INCREASE OF (OH⁻) ACTIVITY AT 35°C)

Miscellaneous	pH	(OH ⁻) activity S	η_s/η_0	Values of R	
				Observed	Calculated
Eqn. (5)	6.80	1.59×10^{-7}	3.58	1.00	1.00
$s_0 = 1.59 \times 10^{-7}$	8.80	1.59×10^{-8}	3.44	0.95	0.98
$m = 0.332$	9.50	7.94×10^{-8}	3.39	0.93	0.93
	10.10	3.16×10^{-4}	3.22	0.86	0.83
$m_0 = 2.72 \times 10^{-4}$	10.54	8.71×10^{-4}	2.93	0.75	0.75

TABLE 2(b)—(VARIATION OF R WITH INCREASE OF H⁺ ION ACTIVITY AT 35°C)

Miscellaneous	pH	(H ⁺) activity S	η_s/η_0	Values of R	
				Observed	Calculated
Eqn. (5)	6.80	1.59×10^{-7}	3.67	1.00	1.00
$s_0 = 1.59 \times 10^{-7}$	5.80	1.59×10^{-8}	3.35	0.88	0.88
$m = 0.31$	5.50	3.16×10^{-8}	3.28	0.85	0.83
$m_0 = 0.23 \times 10^{-5}$	4.52	3.02×10^{-5}	2.90	0.71	0.71

TABLE 3—(VARIATION OF η_{sp}/C WITH C IN NaCl SOLUTION AT 35°C)

Miscellaneous	(SCMC) per cent C	Values of η_{sp}/C	
		Observed	Calculated
NaCl=0.000214N	0.0882	55.6	55.7
	0.0735	58.4	57.4
Eqn. (4)	0.0588	60.9	59.8
$\kappa_1 = 45.8$			
$m = 0.034$	0.0441	64.6	63.5
$m_0 = 0.0123$	0.0294	69.4	69.6
	0.0147	80.7	82.4
NaCl=0.000214N	0.0147	80.7	80.6
Eqn. (6a)	0.0072	70.3	71.6
$B = 63.0$	0.0022	65.6	65.6
$D = 1.2 \times 10^8$			
NaCl=0.000521N	0.994	45.3	46.0
Eqn. (4)	0.0852	47.6	46.8
$\kappa_1 = 38.4$	0.0710	48.9	48.4
$m = 0.046$	0.0568	51.2	50.1
$m_0 = 0.022$	0.0497	53.92	51.1
	0.0426	53.0	52.7
	0.286	54.2	56.7
NaCl=0.000521N	0.0220	—	56.7
Eqn. (6a)	0.0142	51.7	52.1
$B = 45.0$	0.0071	48.8	48.5
$D = 5 \times 10^8$			
NaCl=0.001516N	0.0753	30.5	31.5
Eqn. (6b)	0.0568	28.6	28.6
$B_1 = 19.5$	0.0426	27.1	26.3
$D_1 = 160$	0.0355	26.3	25.2
	0.0213	22.9	22.9
	0.0071	20.4	20.6

TABLE 4—(VARIATION OF η_{sp}/C WITH C IN KCl SOLUTION AT 35°C)

Miscellaneous	(SCMC) per cent C	Value of η_{sp}/C	
		Observed	Calculated
KCl = 0.00041N	0.0990	33.1	33.6
Eqn. (4)	0.0880	34.4	34.3
$\kappa_1 = 27.2$			
$m = 0.048$	0.0770	34.8	35.1
$m_0 = 0.02$	0.0660	36.9	36.1
	0.0550	36.6	37.4
	0.0440	39.9	39.1
	0.0330	42.2	41.6
	0.0220	45.1	45.3
KCl = 0.000416N	0.0220	45.1	47.7
Eqn. (6a)			
B = 38.9	0.0110	44.6	43.3
D = 4×10^2	0.0050	40.9	40.9
KCl = 0.001864N			
Eqn. (6b)	0.0768	28.4	28.4
	0.0640	28.2	27.6
$B_1 = 23.5$	0.0517	26.9	26.8
$D_1 = 64.0$	0.0256	26.2	25.1
	0.0128	24.3	24.3

TABLE 5—(VARIATION OF SPECIFIC CONDUCTIVITY OF (SCMC) WITH DILUTION BY WATER)

Miscellaneous	(SCMC) per cent C	Specific conductivity $\times 10^{-4}$	
		Observed	Calculated
Eqn. (7)	0.270	9.29	9.16
$\lambda'_s = 33.6 \times 10^{-4}$	0.135	4.529	4.626
$\lambda_t = 9 \times 10^{-6}$	0.068	2.337	2.375
	0.034	1.260	1.233
	0.017	0.653	0.661
	0.008	0.353	0.359

In Table 1 are recorded the data taken from Table 1 of the paper of Basu and Das Gupta⁴. In column 1 of the table under the head 'Miscellaneous', the equation used and the value of each of the constants in the equation have been mentioned.

The data recorded in the Tables 2(a) and 2(b) of this paper have been collected from Table 2 of the paper of the aforesaid authors⁴.

The data recorded in the Tables 3, 4 and 5 of this paper have been collected from the Tables 3, 4 and 7 respectively of the paper of Basu and Das Gupta⁴.

Discussion

It may be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that the observed values of η_{sp}/C for different values of C agree well those calculated from equation (4). The observed value of η_{sp}/C at C = 0.07 per cent is higher than that at C = 0.053 per cent of (SCMC). It is probable that at C = 0.07 per cent, the second order electroviscous effect owing to the interaction of the double layers of the macromolecules of (SCMC) is just making itself felt. Equation (4) deals with primary electroviscous effect only and hence the value of η_{sp}/C calculated from it may be a little low.

It is apparent from the data recorded in the Tables 2(a) and 2(b) that the values of R calculated from equation (5) agree well with those observed. It may be pointed out that when the pH is diminished by adding HCl to the (SCMC) sol then below pH 4.52 equation (5) is no longer applicable as most of the COO-Na groups of SCMC are then converted to the COOH groups.

The data recorded in Table 3 show that at NaCl concentration equal to 0.000214, when the concentration of (SCMC) is varied from 0.088 per cent to 0.0147 per cent the values of η_{sp}/C calculated from equation (4) agree well with those observed. At or near C = 0.0147 per cent η_{sp}/C attains its maximum value. From this value of C, η_{sp}/C decreases linearly as C decreases according to equation (6a). In this region, the ζ potential of the macromolecules decreases, owing to hydrolysis, as C decreases.

At NaCl concentration equal to 0.000521N the variation of η_{sp}/C when C is varied from 0.099 per cent to 0.0284 per cent can be quantitatively accounted for by equation (4). It may be noted that η_{sp}/C attains its maximum value between 0.028 and 0.022 per cent of (SCMC) and this maximum value is less than that at NaCl concentration equal to 0.000214N.

At NaCl concentration equal to 0.001516N, η_{sp}/C varies linearly with C and its values calculated by using equation (6b) agree well with those observed. At this relatively high concentration of NaCl, C in the denominator of the right hand side expression of equation (3) can be neglected compared to $K_0 \lambda_t/\lambda_s$ and equation (3) then assumes the form of equation (6b).

The data recorded in Table 4 show that at KCl concentration equal to 0.000416N, variation of η_{sp}/C with C can be quantitatively accounted for by equation (4) when C lies between 0.099 and 0.022 per cent and by equation (6a) when C lies between 0.022 and 0.005 per cent of (SCMC).

At KCl concentration equal to $0.001864N$ η_{sp}/C varies linearly with C according to equation (6b).

The data recorded in Table 5 show that the variation of specific conductivity of the (SCMC) sol with dilution by water can be represented fairly satisfactorily by equation (7). Since equation (7) is only an approximate form of equation (2) so the application of the latter to the (SCMC) system is justified.

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